

IMPROVING LISTENING AMONG ELEMENTARY PUPILS

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Annotation. This article discusses the ways and methods of solving problems related to listening skills in the process of teaching foreign languages to children.

Key words: interactive methods, step exercises, “Spelling” method.

In our daily lives, listening is essential. People listen for a range of motives each day, consisting of entertainment, tutorial goals, and acquiring required information. It is imperative to study languages due to the fact that, they enable people to gain insights and facts as well as to communicate effectively with others. Listening is an essential factor in gaining knowledge of English as foreign languages. Other skills, such as writing, reading, and speaking, show up to be much less significant than listening, which is the most extensively used talent on a daily basis. Listening is a type of communication. It is one of a language’s four skills. According to the data, humans spend between 70% and 80% of their days engaged in some form of communication, and about 55% of their time is devoted to listening. Moreover, listening is the most interesting part while learning language.

This can lead us to alter our grasp of the world around us. “Never give up listening”. “Of all the capabilities of leadership, listening is the most treasured—and one of the least understood”. Most captains of enterprise pay attention only sometimes, and they stay everyday leaders. But a few, the magnificent ones, in no way quit listening. That’s how they get word earlier than everyone else of unseen problems and opportunities. — Peter Nulty, Fortune Magazine

However, many scholars, especially elementary pupils have problems with listening skill because English is a new language for them. At that time, they do not understand sufficient phrases in this language, or they only hear the words. For these reasons, they have many challenges to memorize fundamental phrases throughout the listening. Ann Anderson and Tony Lynch point out in their e-book referred to as “Listening” that “Young listeners with terrible memory and listening skills are no longer helped by the extra facts in redundant messages because there are too many records for them to process”. That’s why they endorsed the use of tasks made up of simple phrases for youth of junior class age during the lesson.

To enhance pupils’ listening talents, instructors need to pay more attention throughout the class and teacher in less difficult ways. In addition to this, parents should additionally help their children extend their listening skills. In this article, I show the approaches for creating listening skills. There are many video games for young people that teachers may also teach. For example, the game that is referred to as “Musical chairs”. In this method, all the pupils stand up, and the teacher asks them a question. Then audio is played; as soon as the pupils hear the answer, they have to sit down. The remaining one sitting down loses. What they can also do is they can do an activity bounce like rabbits, world like a zombie. As soon as they hear the reply, they have to stop. This is just an exciting factor to keep college students busy and also a main point for listening. One of the interesting games is “Simon Says”. Simon says, “Touch your ear”, Simon says, “Rub your head, and Simon says, “Jump up”. Kids love this game because it gets them active. Teachers can also increase the listening factor by saying, Simon says, “Touch something starting with the

letter “A””. Students run around the class and find something that starts with the letter “A”. They can also do riming and other things. It is only up to teachers’ own imaginations, but this is a great one to use. It is a fantastic game to use for the lesson with elementary students.

The dictation method is also useful for improving the listening skills of young students. Depending on the class of pupils, the teacher will say words that are easier or slightly more difficult. For example, for 2nd graders, teachers may use the “Spelling” method, which improves both writing and listening skills.

Every language lesson usually starts with a warm-up or some task to make people think about the topic they are about to learn. The listening lesson is made up of three stages, regardless of the framework that teachers use. These are the three stages that make up a listening lesson.

Pre-Listening Activities.

The pre-listening stage helps pupils prepare for what they are going to hear, and this offers them an extended chance of success in any given task. Pre-listening tasks can help teachers stumble on out what elementary pupils already comprehend about the topic, help mitigate the anxiety that comes from listening in a remote place language by way of imparting a clear context, and offer opportunities for class dialogue and greater interplay amongst students.

While-Listening Activities.

During-listening duties are a sequence of things to do that a learner does even as they listen to a passage in order to exhibit their appreciation of what they have heard. While listening activities can help to identify what’s critical in a passage, perceive the textual content’s material structure, and keep themselves focused all through the passage. Moreover, these activities can aid in focusing attention on listening for special information and listening for the speaker’s way of thinking or opinion.

Post-Listening Activities.

Post-Listening Activities consist of duties whose essential intention is to help elementary pupils replicate the listening experience. These matters to do are carried out after the coach has carried out pre-listening and while listening to things to do successfully. Post-listening activities can help pupils learn to summarize the information they heard, and when teachers ask students to have a quick discussion about the topic, the theme for the discussion must be taken from the listening project that they beforehand did and must be fascinating enough to inspire comments and debates.

As stated above, listening is one of the most interesting phases of studying English. Increased listening all through the lesson also helps to enhance speaking. As Bernard Baruch said, “Most of the profitable people I have recognized are the ones who do more listening than talking”. By being a suitable listener, people get a whole lot more than being a big talker. They analyze different people and understand what makes them tick. Moreover, to increase listening, it is really helpful to watch extra cartoons and movies with subtitles and listen to songs from a young age. When pupils watch with full attention, they absorb new records about any type of theme and build many new structures that assist their grammar. In addition, they communicate fluently. Finally, getting the child interested in listening in class will additionally assist him in improving his other skills.

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